
Threats to critical Infrastructure and Oil theft in Niger Delta Region of Nigeria: Examination of complexities between Security Agencies and Non-State Actors.

By

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Abstract

The Niger Delta region of Nigeria, known for its vast resources, has faced persistent threats to its critical infrastructure and oil theft. The research objective is to investigate threats to critical infrastructure and oil theft, as well as to examine the complexities between security agencies and non-state actors. Data were collected from secondary sources, and the situation Crime prevention theory serves as a theoretical framework, emphasizing the need to reduce crime through environmental and structural interventions. The findings revealed that some security personnel collaborate with non-state actors, undermining regional efforts to protect critical assets. As a result, the study suggests that security be viewed as a collaborative effort involving the government, private sector, and the entire citizenry, as this will shift the focus from reactive response to crime to crime prevention and partnership building. Punishment must be certain and sufficient in magnitude to serve as a deterrent and government should invest in productive capacities of local communities as this will provide alternative livelihoods thereby reducing the resort to oil theft and the destruction of critical government infrastructure.

Key Words: Critical Infrastructure, Oil Theft, Non –State Actors, Security Agencies.

Background to the study.

The Nigerian government is dealing with rising insecurity. Kidnappings of innocent people, armed robberies, human trafficking, murders motivated by religion, conflicts between tribes or communities, terrorism, criminal activity by gangsters or cultists, and banditry, pipeline vandalism, crude oil theft, sea robbery, and other maritime illegalities in Nigeria's backwaters have recently increased to alarming levels. Its economic impact, as shown by Nigeria's oil regulator report, reveals that the country lost 141 million barrels of crude oil, an equivalent of \$1 billion in revenue in the first quarter of 2022.

Poverty, unemployment, and underdevelopment had exacerbated the struggle for resource control in the Niger Delta region. Access to large quantities of small arms and light weapons, combined with widespread dissatisfaction with the federal and state governments in the Niger Delta region, provides a fertile recruiting ground for MEND and other militant organizations (International Crisis Group, 2006).

The insecurity currently plaguing Nigeria has put critical national infrastructure and assets at risk. Critical infrastructure is defined as a collection of systems that have a significant impact on the state's security and, by extension, the security of its citizens (Ewa, 2020). Commercial buildings, emergency services, energy, food, industry, health, transportation, gas, public communications, radio and television, and the chemical and nuclear industries are all examples of critical infrastructure. According to Adigun (2018), sustainable development requires a strong infrastructure foundation. The country's security, economic health, and public safety are all dependent on the effective protection of its critical infrastructure. Development is guaranteed when these infrastructure facilities are secured and efficient.

The Nigerian Police Force, which has statutory responsibility for internal security, has been unable to contain violence and insecurity in Nigeria. The majority of people believe that the Nigerian police falls short of their expectations. The Nigerian Police is viewed as a toothless dog that can only bark but not bite. According to Odekunle (2004), police performance has been hampered by a combination of material and human factors. Inadequate funding for police development, such as training, logistics, arms, and ammunition, and underutilization of funds impede effective police performance.

In response to internal security challenges and threats to infrastructure and critical assets, the Nigerian government deployed the military and other security agencies to assist the police force. Unfortunately, corruption in the defense sector undermines the military's ability to respond to national security (Ezeajughu, 2021). Soldiers' conduct only worsens the country's security situation, with evidence of lack of professionalism, intimidation, coercion, and extortion at military checkpoints.

Individuals, communities, and institutions' growing desire for increased security to combat rising insecurity in Nigeria has resulted in the emergence of several non-state actors, whether or not they are recognized by the government. Indeed, the proliferation of non-state actors has recently led some international relations observers to conclude that states are losing importance while non-state actors gain status and influence. To combat rising insecurity, the federal government called on non-state actors to protect the country's maritime environment. The Federal Government hired Tantita Security Services Limited, a private security firm owned by Mr Government Ekpemupolo, also known as Tompolo, a former militant leader in the Niger Delta, to secure the region's oil pipelines. Tantita's men have recently clashed with the Nigerian Navy and non-state actors over the capture of oil thieves' vessels.

Taking the scale of the infraction, this research is geared towards investigating if there is conspiracy between state security agencies and non –state actors in the protection of infrastructures and critical national assets in Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.

Statement of the problem.

Insecurity has long plagued the country's oil-rich Niger Delta region. The Niger Delta Region is inherently unstable, with numerous warlords and militias vying for power and a larger share of the government's payoff. Insecurity and a sense of helplessness among Nigerians are now serious issues with far-reaching consequences. In addition, insecurity has had a significant impact on Niger Delta investments. International companies and private investors have avoided the area, citing security concerns. Competition for oil wealth has fueled corruption and, eventually, violence among countless ethnic groups, leading to the militarization of nearly the entire Niger-Delta region by ethnic militia groups, the Nigerian military, the Nigerian police, and other security agencies. The crisis of governance is at the heart of Nigeria's systemic failure, as evidenced by the state's declining ability to cope with a wide range of internal political, economic, and social upheavals (Obasi & Iwara, 2021). The destruction and loss of critical infrastructure's operational capacity poses a threat to the state's structural and personal security, as critical infrastructure plays an important role in ensuring national security (Ewa, 2020). The non-state actors have actually been emboldened to use sophisticated and lethal means to vandalize strategic and important national assets with impunity as a result of the security agencies' lackadaisical attitude to the law and lack of application of full kinetic measures. They have also continued their nefarious activities, which include oil bunkering, oil theft, illegal modular refineries, kidnapping for ransom, pipeline vandalism, and even engaging the security agencies in physical combat to extract money from oil companies and the Nigerian government. According to a number of studies, security agents' corruption and duty-related neglect have given criminals an excuse to continue their business, which in turn causes insecurity (Olaniyan & Aliyu, 2016, Amusan, Agunyai, & Ayodele, 2022).

Attacks on critical infrastructure and oil theft pose serious risks to public safety, economic stability and national security. To tackle and address these threats necessitate ascertaining if complexities exist between security agencies and non-state actors in oil theft and the protection of infrastructure and critical national assets in Nigeria's Niger Delta region.

Objective of the Study

The purpose of this paper is to critically analyze the threat to critical assets, the phenomenon of oil theft, and the presumed conspiracies between non-state actors and security agencies.

Methodology

The study takes an exploratory and qualitative approach. Secondary data served as the foundation for data collection, interpretation, and analysis in order to meet the goals of this research. A thorough evaluation of pertinent literature on the topic of the investigation was used to gather data.

Conceptual Clarification

Critical infrastructure

Systems that are directly tied to energy security, telecommunications, energy systems, gas and oil pipelines, the economy, transportation, water supply, and waterways that support the

State's effective operation are classified as critical infrastructure by DCSINT (2006). In order for society to operate efficiently and to guarantee the general well-being of its members, critical infrastructure is essential. This covers things like electricity installations, oil pipelines and refineries, transportation, the economy, dams, education facilities, telecommunications and information communication technology, and so forth (DCSINT, 2006).

Critical infrastructure, according to Akaraz and Zeadally (2015), is a group of real or virtual systems that are essential to a nation and whose disruption could have a detrimental impact on national security, economic prosperity, public health, or any combination of these actors. Everything that is said about what critical infrastructures are points to the fact that they are necessities for the state, its economy, and the general welfare of society. They are also amenities of socioeconomic benefit and security value. The well-being of society and the efficient operation of government would automatically suffer from any attack on such amenities (Obina, 2022).

Security

It is difficult to define security because it has been interpreted differently in many historical contexts. Security has traditionally been understood to mean a nation's military preparedness to repel external threats. Traditional security entails a state possessing sufficient military power to prevent conflict and, in the event that it arises, uphold essential principles via triumph

"A country's capacity to resist external or internal threats to its physical survival or core values" is how Nkwede and Alegu (2018) define traditional security. Traditional security is the state's ability to maintain sovereignty, protect territorial integrity, maintain peace and stability, and engage in armed conflict. The end of the Cold War in the 1990s, however, signaled a paradigm shift and a fundamental departure from the traditional security approach, which was state-centric and focused on the military might of the state, to the modern approach, which is people-centered and human-centered. The need to abandon the traditional understanding of security and adopt a people-centered or individual-centered approach appears to be largely due to the admixture and convergence of a number of factors, such as the failure of liberal state building through the Washington consensus's instruments, the rise in violent internal conflicts in Africa, East Europe, and Asia, the acceleration of globalization, the exponential increase in the spread and consolidation of democracy, and the inability of neoliberal development models to stimulate economic growth in developing countries or systematically address the effects of complex (Okolie & Nnamai, 2017).

Oil Theft.

The most traded commodity on the planet is still oil(OPEC, 2019). An uncontrolled market has unavoidably been created by the global demand for such a valuable and transportable good. Oil can travel the whole distance outside of legally permitted channels of exchange, or it can leave and reenter the controlled value chain at any time. In addition to undermining the legitimate oil industry, uncontrolled oil movements also pose a threat to the organizations that support the legal production and international trade of oil. The very basis of the oil industry, and consequently the Nigerian economy, is at risk due to the problem of oil theft and illicit bunkering activities in the Niger Delta (Garuba, 2012).

According to Asuni (2009), oil theft includes the theft of oil from pipelines or flow stations as well as the unaccounted-for addition of excess crude oil to legitimate cargo. According to Obasi (2011), "illegal oil bunkering" as used in Nigeria refers to any act involving the theft, diversion, and smuggling of oil, not just the unauthorized loading of ships. Oil theft in the

Niger Delta has grown to an industrial scale, involving commodity traders, international criminals, and a wide network of individuals (Uwaezuoke & Ogunmade, 2013).

Nigeria faces severe challenges from oil theft. Massive revenue losses to Nigeria's monoproducer economy, constant equipment and pipeline vandalism, frequent fire outbreaks that result in operator fatalities, decreased investor profit, and a lack of trust from foreign investors are some of the repercussions. Additional repercussions include ongoing oil spills that damage and contaminate the environment of the host community, including soil and water (both surface and subsurface). Additionally, these lead to the disruption and devastation of traditional occupations such as farming. In addition to funding illegal activities that harm society, such as drug and human trafficking (Uduji et al., 2019; Williams, 2009), uncontrolled oil movements can also spark civil wars (Basedau & Roy, 2020). To government agencies and oil companies, oil theft and all of its consequences verges on criminal activity and economic sabotage. The "new face of terrorism" is what it is. However, the view is completely different in the Niger Delta's local communities, where it is viewed as a "display of local expertise" (Biakpara, 2012), and an innovative free market reaction to persistent energy shortages, local economic dysfunction, and the government's inability to provide essential public services (SDN Report, 2013). The Delta's residents feel entitled to a portion of the region's enormous oil wealth because of the lack of development and environmental destruction. It has been proven that those who are involved in crude oil theft include employees of the International Oil Companies, retired and serving military and security personnel, officials of the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation, indigenous oil producers, top politicians and their enablers (Osah, 2020) Non – State actors.

There is a direct correlation between the rise in non-state actors and the levels of economic, political, social, and cultural exchanges between people, communities, and states. Recently, some analysts of international relations have concluded that the growth of NSAs is elevating the status of non-state actors. NSAs are described as "non-sovereign entities that exercise significant economic, political, or social power and influence at a national and at international levels" by the US National Intelligence Council in 2007.

This definition encompasses entities such as non-governmental organizations (NGOs), multinational corporations (MNCs), terrorists, and criminal networks. In development cooperation, the term "NSA" is frequently used. For example, the Cotonou Agreement between the European Union (EU) and the countries of Africa, the Caribbean, and the Pacific (ACP) widely acknowledges the role of non-state actors as "a wide range of nongovernmental development actors" whose involvement is crucial to the cooperation between the EU and ACP. Article 6 of the Cotonou Agreement states that economic and social partners, such as trade union organizations, the private sector, and civil society in all of its diversity based on national characteristics are all included in NSAs. This implies that all types of actors, including trade unions, universities and research institutes, women's groups, human rights associations, farmers' cooperatives, trade associations, and the private sector, are welcome to participate. Informal groups like unofficial private sector associations and grassroots organizations are also covered by this definition. However, the private sector is only taken into account when it comes to its involvement in non-profit organizations such as chambers of commerce, private sector associations, etc. Today, the term "non-state actor" refers to any association or group that falls under the purview of CSOs or NGOs and works to influence public policy for the benefit of society as a whole (Akpan, 2011).

Non-state actors can be both violent and non-violent, according to Wapmuk (2012), depending on the political objectives they aim to accomplish. The violent NSAs try to attain their objectives by violent means, whereas the non-violent NSAs (such as MNCs, NGOs, and charitable organizations and individuals) try to do so through non-violent means. These objectives may be driven by aspirations that are religious, ideological, or ethnic. These encompass a broad spectrum of organizations with diverse goals, ranging from those aiming to topple an established state's government to those desiring increased autonomy within their respective regions

The emergence of militant youths and the agitation for resource control by Niger Delta indigenous peoples shifted the course of illegal activity. At the start of the agitation in the Niger Delta, the primary goal was political, with citizens demanding an increase in the derivation fund. However, when the government failed to meet their demand, many of the youths took up arms against the government and engaged in criminal activities such as kidnapping, destruction of oil facilities, oil theft, and piracy.

Theoretical Framework

Situational Crime prevention Theory.

This study is based on Ronald Clarke's situational crime prevention theory. This viewpoint focuses on how crime can be reduced by altering the situational or spatial features of an environment. The theory held that crime can be effectively reduced by changing circumstances rather than an offender's personal dispositions. It implements discrete managerial and environmental changes to reduce the opportunity for crime to occur.

It aims to eliminate criminal or delinquent tendencies by improving society or its institutions and making criminal activities less appealing to offenders (Clarke, 1992). It entails developing methods to prevent, limit, or disrupt criminal activity. Clarke (1992) describes how these techniques use a variety of environmental manipulations to change the risks, efforts, and rewards of offending. The foundation of this theory is based on the assumptions that more opportunities lead to more crime, easier ones attract more offenders, and the presence of easy opportunities allows for a "life of crime."

According to the situational crime prevention theory, society contributes to the inadvertent creation of crime by producing "criminogenic goods," leaking systems, and poor facility management/design. As a result, society must develop new ideas that have lower economic and social costs. As a result, situational crime prevention entails measures aimed at highly specific types of crime that involve systematically and permanently managing, designing, or manipulating the immediate environment (Clarke, 1983). Crime prevention requires four major strategies: target hardening, access control, deflecting offenders, and controlling facilitators.

Weak institutions of government make oversight a challenge resulting in breakdown of discipline, integrity and accountability. With weak application of rule of law, the judiciary is hampered in holding security personnel and non –state actors accountable for illegal activities and their involvement often goes unpunished. Thus, benefits that go with involvement in illegal activities outweigh the risk associated with the act.

Examination of complexities between Security Personnel and Non-State actors in the Protection of Critical Infrastructure and Oil Theft in Niger Delta.

Notwithstanding the government's military action to mitigate the challenges of insecurity in the Niger Delta, attacks on oil facilities and other critical assets have continued to persist, raising concerns about partnerships between security agencies and non-state actors in the region.

The inelastic demand for oil, has forced most actors to circumvent formal rules and regulations in order to profit from unofficial value chains. Oil theft can occur at any stage of the production chain, from the well head to the retail pump. Oil theft however is not for the poor, it is an extensive racket involving the military, security apparatchiks, politicians, dubious industrial moguls and the oil companies (Okwelum, 2021), but Non-state actors show up as skilful players who can quickly take advantage of opportunities brought about by authority lapses and more easily adjust to countermeasures.

Local communities, foreign buyers, criminal syndicates, and militant groups are among the non-state actors engaged in oil theft in Nigeria (Ikelegbe, 2005). The challenging terrain, lax enforcement of regulations, and worldwide demand for oil have all been exploited by militants, in particular, to establish profitable markets for stolen crude (Igbinovia, 2014). According to Watts (2004), their actions are frequently seen as a direct reaction to their marginalization and exclusion from the advantages of oil wealth.

Since the early 2000s, a Joint Task Force (JTF) of Nigerian Army, Air Force, Navy, and Police personnel has been deployed in the Niger Delta region. The JTF is tasked with combating the region's militant threat and preventing oil theft. However, there have been indications that some JTF members are complicit in, and frequently benefit from, the very pursuit they are supposed to eradicate (Transparency International, 2019).

Finding demonstrates that members of Nigeria's armed forces have facilitated and profited from the illegal trade in a variety of ways. This benefit is frequently obtained by providing "protection" in exchange for financial bribes, such as ensuring military officials turn a blind eye to illegal activity and protecting oil thieves' access to extraction points from adversaries (Stakeholder Democracy Network, 2015, Adebayo 2022).

A Chatham House report suggests that JTF officers have stood guard at illegal tap points and provided armed escorts to ships loaded with stolen crude (Chatham House, 2013; Ezirim, 2020). Similarly, a 2015 report from the Stakeholder Democracy Network (SDN) reports JTF members' active involvement in oil theft, ranging from providing security to local oil thieves as they install taps that divert oil from pipelines to collecting "transportation taxes" for oil-transporting vehicles and demanding "regional security payments" from illegal oil refineries for ongoing protection.

According to research, military personnel organized and systematically solicit payment from oil thieves at military checkpoints. Evidence in Port Harcourt indicates that those trading oil products could pay charges ahead of time to ensure easy passage through checkpoints and eliminate the possibility of seizure. They must declare the exact quantity of goods to be transported through the checkpoint and pay a contact in advance. When the vehicle passes through the checkpoint, military personnel verify that the declared quantity matches the actual cargo. Any discrepancies could lead to the vehicle and products being seized (Transparency International, 2019). In fact, Omede (2021) stated that the military allegedly covers up oil theft by destroying evidence, intimidating witnesses, and silencing whistleblowers.

Soldiers have been accused of selling or hiring weapons to armed groups, as well as encouraging fighting among groups (Isumonah, 2013). According to an International Crisis Group (2022) report, the military collaborates with non-state actors in the Niger Delta, providing them with weapons and intelligence in exchange for a share of the stolen oil.

The military wants to stay in the Niger Delta because they make a lot of money escorting illegally bunkered crude and extorting money in the name of road security (Uranta, 2009). The issue is that security personnel have been found to be complicit in massive oil theft in the Niger Delta. According to credible allegations, senior military personnel are directly involved in industrial-scale theft (Punch, 2023). The foot soldiers are not the only ones who profit; the Commissioner of Police, the Director of State Security Services, and the Military all line up at the Governor's door, asking for 'favours,' according to Kemedi (Daily Trust, April 13, 2011). Two admirals were removed from duty after being found guilty of stealing and selling oil in the Delta (Polgreen, 2006). Governor Ekpemupolo, alias Tompolo, admitted that it is difficult to break the firm grip of oil bunkers in the Niger Delta because of the protection they receive from security personnel (Vanquard, 2023).

This explained why the military will never use its full force to crush the militia. It was also revealed that at night, trucks typically made their way to a loading point near some creeks in Bayelsa state, from which illegally refined products were transported to various parts of the country. Some security agents along that route turn a blind eye during such movements, allowing illegally refined petroleum products to travel freely throughout the state and beyond. Even when some of these trucks were impounded by naval personnel assigned to NNS SOROH, so-called eminent members of society would pester naval authorities with requests for their release. Sometimes owners contacted higher authorities to press for the trucks' release (Usman, 2022).

Conclusion.

The cooperation of non-state actors and the military to safeguard government critical infrastructure, especially oil facilities, has grown to be a contentious topic with inconsistent outcomes. While some state actors work closely with the security agencies, others are still heavily involved in oil theft and facility destruction in connivance with security personnel, which are linked to political grievances, the recession, lax law enforcement, and poor governance.

Recommendations.

The following recommendations are made based on research findings.

The obligation for protecting critical infrastructure should not be placed solely on the government; all stakeholders in the country must be involved.

Law enforcement agencies and community members must collaborate to protect these infrastructures.

There should be regular training and retraining for technocrats who can manage critical infrastructure in the oil industry that requires technical input.

The government should promote community policing as a means of gathering intelligence and ensuring a proactive approach to critical infrastructure management in the oil industry.

There should be a free toll hotline for emergency purposes, and the public should be properly informed of its availability.

The government must ensure that those responsible for the destruction of critical infrastructure face harsher penalties.

Punishment must be certain and sufficient in magnitude to serve as a deterrent.

Investing in productive capacities of local communities will provide alternative livelihoods thereby reducing the resort to oil theft and the destruction of critical government infrastructure.

All stakeholders in the oil sector must consider upgrading and maintaining oil infrastructure to make it more resistant to theft and sabotage.

Increasing transparency in the oil industry, as well as improving oversight and accountability will help address increasing oil theft.

Better public education and awareness campaigns are needed to emphasize the importance of safeguarding the government's vital infrastructure.

The government should think about offering rewards and assurances of safety to informants who reveal identity theft and the damage of vital government infrastructure.

Using advanced surveillance technologies like drones, satellite monitoring, and CCTV to monitor oil infrastructure. Working with international organizations and governments to address the global scale of oil theft.

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